

Implementation Guide

In this document, we present how to use the transformation process implemented.

Step 1 ATL

As mention in the paper, our implementation of the transformation process is based on the ATL a model transformation language and toolkit. ATL model transformation language is developed on top of the Eclipse platform (install ATL in Eclipse IDE). After installing ATL language organise the files provided in this directory for the ATL in the workspace as presented in the figure below (Metamodels, Models, and Transformations).

To run the ATL it need the input (the feature model: Feature_model.xmi (in models)) and the output will be the generated model in xmi format (GeneratedModel.xmi in models). GeneratedModel is the the xmi file of the runtime CBVM.

Step 2 Code generation

Now, The generated XML file is parsed using the DOM library in Java to generate the JavaBIP specification and the glue coordination. In the same manner organise your directory as presented in the figure below (Java files provided in the zenodo). As presented the input the the generated xmi specification and the output is the JavaBIP specification and the glue coordination.

Step 3: testing and evaluation reproducing

After having produced the javaBIP specifications and the glue. Copy the java files created into a new project and add the jar files (jar files provided in the zenedo repo).

Once you added the jar files to the same repository (e.g. put jar files in folder lib beside the src folder of the translation project) you will be able to test and execute using the user interface.

Also apart from the heroku cloud example a mobile phone example is provided. Do not hesitate to create new feature model you would like to examine.

